

Experimental base, Chelopechene district, Sofia

First experiment

07 June 2024

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This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action under grant agreement No 101000224.

Results of the first experiments Chelopechene district test field

Latitude (WGS84); decimal degree (+: North, -:South) - 42.739722

Longitude (WGS84); decimal degree (+: East, -: West) - 23.467778

total area of the experiment (m²) - 602

plots/design of the experiment-long plots with 8 treatments 602m² total

main crop - tree crops

irrigated area - > 25%

experiment aimed at investigating the impact of irrigation management for apple trees; Long term experiment

plots/design of the experiment- Chelopechene experimental field_6treatments

long plots with 6 treatments (24 m² each)

main crop- horticultural crops;

irrigated area- 192 m²

experiment aimed at investigating the impact of irrigation and fertigation management for greenhouse vegetables; Long term greenhouse experiment

At Chelopechene experimental field, trials are conducted with different agricultural crops such as, for example:

1. Determination of the irrigation regime of alfalfa grown on leached cinnamon forest soil in the area of experimental field "Chelopechene"

On the territory of the Experimental Field "Chelopechene" of IPAZR "N. Pushkarov" an experiment was conducted with alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*, L.), variety "Pleven 6". The test field is part of the Sofia field, located at 550 m above sea level. The soil at the experimental site is leached cinnamon forest, uneroded to slightly eroded.

It is characterized by the following agrochemical indicators: humus – 1.61%; mineral nitrogen – 8.6 mg/kg; mobile phosphorus (P₂O₅) – 13.5 mg/100 g; mobile potassium (K₂O) – 23.0 mg/100g; pH (H₂O) – 6.1.

The water-physical properties for the layer 0 – 0.20 m (0.60 m) are as follows: marginal field moisture capacity (PPV) - 21.8 % (22.12%) relative to the weight of the absolutely dry soil; bulk soil weight at PPV – 1.50 g/cm³ (1.47 g/cm³) and wilting moisture – 10.8% (10.4%) relative to the weight of absolutely dry soil.

The aim of this research is to determine the optimal irrigation regime of alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*, L.), variety "Pleven 6". In the first year of crop cultivation, low-pressure micro-jet sprinklers were used for its irrigation. Irrigation was applied at a pre-irrigation soil moisture of 75-80% of PPV. Based on the experimental results, two waterings with an irrigation rate of 15 mm/ha.10-1 were given for seed germination and 7 main irrigations with an irrigation rate of 40 mm/ha.10-1.

The optimal irrigation rate for 2018 was established in the amount of 310 mm/ha. The number of waterings is determined depending on the weather conditions of the year. Four waterings were carried out in the flowering phase with an average dry weight yield (hay) of 530 kg/ha.10-1. Regarding the air temperature, the year 2018 is characterized as the warmest for the period with a guarantee of 1.16%, and the guarantee of the amount of precipitation for the period April-September is 6.13% (476 mm - 2018).

2. Establishing the main technological parameters of the drip irrigation system for raspberries

Fertilization: Conventional fertilizers, ammonium nitrate and, if necessary, phosphorus and potassium fertilizers.

The experiment was performed using the long plot method in four replicates. Determination of the irrigation regime.

To monitor the dynamics of soil moisture, soil samples were taken in 3-10 days at a depth of 0.50 m every 0.10 m, in three repetitions and processed according to the classical weight thermostat method. On the basis of the obtained results for soil moisture, the necessary irrigation rates are submitted.

The plants are planted in a single-row scheme 3.0 x 0.5 m. with paths of 1.5 m in the end sections. The raspberry plantation was created in 2011 with the repair variety "Lyulin".

In terms of air temperature, the years 2017 and 2018 are characterized as very warm with a guarantee of 6.13 and 1.16%, and in terms of precipitation, they are respectively very dry with a guarantee of 90.56% (2017) and rainy with collateral 7.78% (2018). During the growing season of the crop from May to September, depending on the soil moisture indicators, 23 waterings were implemented with an irrigation rate of 167.8 m³/ha and an irrigation rate of 3,860 m³/ha, respectively, for all tested irrigation wings. And in 2018, 11 irrigations were implemented with an irrigation rate of 167.8 m³/ha to m³/ha and an irrigation rate of 1,850 m³/ha, respectively, with subsoil drip irrigation while maintaining a pre-irrigation humidity of 80 to 100 PPV.

In the non-irrigated variant, a yield of 1.5 (2018) to 2.30 (2017) t/ha was obtained. In the drought during mass fruiting, the fruits began to dry. The rainfall during the critical phases of development – flowering and mass fruiting of the crop was ineffective and insufficient. The effect of irrigation is nearly 300%.

1. During the growing season of the crop from April to September in 2017, depending on the indicators of soil moisture, 23 waterings were carried out with an irrigation rate of 3,860 m³/ha. Due to a difference in meteorological indicators in 2018, it was necessary to supply 11 irrigations with an irrigation rate

2. The highest yields under the soil-meteorological conditions in 2017 in the Sofia field were obtained with the option irrigated with 100% implementation of the irrigation rate with the application of subsoil drip irrigation. Its yield is 5.80 t/ha.

3. The differences in the spacing of the droplet generators in both years had an impact on the obtained yields. The highest yield in both studied years was obtained with a PE ϕ 16 mm pipeline, with a distance between the droplet generators $l_k = 0.30$ m and the amount of water flowing from the droplet generator $q_k = 2.0$ l/ha in 2017 from 5.80 t/ha, and in 2018 4.0 t/ha.

4. When the distance between the droplet generators is increased to 0.75 m, there is a decrease in yield on average by 35%, less compared to $l_k = 0.30$ m, $q_k = 2.0$ l/h.

5. From the hydraulic calculations made, it was established that: the maximum distance between the drippers along the length of the wings for the cinnamon forest soil and raspberry remontant variety culture is 0.50 m at a nominal water amount (at 10 m above sea level) of the drippers - 2.0 l/ha and distance between irrigation wings 3.00 m with a diameter of $\phi 16-20$ mm.

3. Influence of the irrigation regime on the yield of the determinant tomato variety "Nicolina" f1 in polish production

The experiment was conducted in 2017-2018 at the Experimental Field of the Nikola Pushkarov Institute of Soil Science Agrotechnologies and Plant Protection in the Chelopechene quarter (42°60'N, 23°46'E and 550 m above sea level) in the Sofia area, with a deterministic variety "Nicolina" tomatoes, grown on leached cinnamon forest soil. The soil in the experimental area is slightly humus (1.44%) with a slightly acidic reaction – pH in H₂O - 6.2; pH in KCl – 5.4. The mineral nitrogen content is low – 16.1 mg.kg⁻¹ soil. The degree of storage with mobile forms of phosphorus and potassium is average - 11.4 mg P.100g⁻¹ and 17.7 mg K.100g⁻¹ soil.

The experiment was carried out according to the block method in four repetitions, with the size of the experimental plot 7.5 m² and the size of the experimental area of one variant - 28.80 m². Irrigation was carried out using a drip irrigation system. Drip irrigation wings are selected according to the wetting contours of cinnamon forest soil, the distance between the drippers is 0.30 m, with a water discharge amount of 2 lh⁻¹. They are placed two in each strip immediately next to the tomato stems on the surface of the field. The plants are planted in a two-row strip according to the scheme 100 + 60 x 30.

Conclusions

1. During the growing season of the crop, from May to September, depending on the soil moisture indicators in the wet year 2018, to maintain the soil moisture in the range of 80% PPV to 100% PPV, 9 waterings with an average irrigation rate were applied (17.50 mm) and irrigation rate respectively – 157.15 mm, at 100% irrigation rate. And in the dry year of 2017, it was necessary to apply three times more – 23 waterings with an average rate (19.54 mm) and an irrigation rate (449.50 mm).

2. In the very dry year 2017, a 2.5 times increase in yield was obtained compared to the wet year 2018. The wet year had an adverse effect on the growth and development of the tomato plantation (root rot on the plants, flower combing, stem drop and attack by fungal diseases on the foliage and fruits)

4. The biometric indicators of the Florina variety apple plantation

On the territory of the experimental field "Chelopechene" of IPAZR "N. Pushkarov" is conducting an experimental experiment with an intensive apple plantation of the Florina variety, created in 2017. The soil in the research area is Leached Cinnamon Forest. When comparing the biometric characteristics of trees grown with drip irrigation and mulching and those without mulching in the period 2020-2022, the results showed that under the influence of mulching, apple trees showed stronger growth in the following indicators: stem circumference, stem cross-section, average tree height and crown volume.

Average stem girth increased from 167 mm to 241 mm when using mulch, and from 140 mm to 218 mm when using no mulch. The average circumference when using mulch is 10% larger. The average tree cross-section increased from 22.66 cm³ in 2020 to 47 cm³ in 2022. when using mulch. And for the version without mulch, it is 16.34 cm³ in 2020 to 31.62 cm³ in 2022.

The average height of the Florina apple tree is 3.25 m to 3.54 m when using mulch and 3.10 m to 3.54 m when using no mulch. There are no significant differences in the height of the trees for the two options. The biggest differences are observed in crown formation/crown volume during the years under review. The main objective is: Investigating the influence of optimal irrigation on the biometric indicators of a super-intensive apple orchard under drip irrigation and mulching.